

FunGlass
centre for functional and
surface functionalized glass

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

FunGlass School 2023/1

Ráztočno

June 19- 21, 2023

ORGANIZING INSTITUTIONS:

FunGlass School 2023/1

Book of Abstracts

Ráztočno, June 19– 21, 2023

SCIENTIFIC BOARD: Dušan Galusek, Prof., DSc., Marek Liška, Prof., DSc., Dr.h.c

REVIEWERS: Dušan Galusek, Prof., DSc., Marek Liška, Prof. DSc., Dr.h.c, Mária Chromčíková, Assoc. Prof., Robert Klement, Assoc.Prof., Amirhossein Pakseresht, Assoc.Prof., José Velázquez, Assoc.Prof., Dr. Dagmar Galusková, Dr. Martin Michálek, Dr. Jozef Kraxner

Edited by Dr. Branislav Hruška and Vanda Mokrářová

ISBN 978-80-8075-993-3

EAN 9788080759933

CONTENTS:

PREPARATION AND STUDY OF CRYSTALLIZATION KINETICS OF YTTRIUM-ALUMINATE GLASSES / A. AKUSEVICH	3
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF ORGANIC DYES AND PHOTOCATALYTIC WATER SPLITTING IN OXIDE AND SULFIDE SEMICONDUCTORS / M. ŽITŇAN	4
SPRAY DRY SYNTHESIS OF FTO BEADS / O. SISMAN	5
INNOVATIVE FUNCTIONALITIES OF ION-EXCHANGED GLASSES / R.DAGUPATI.....	6
GROWTH OF ZIF-8 ON 3D PRINTED CERAMIC ALUMINA STRUCTURE FOR GAS SEPARATION APPLICATION / S.RANA	7
HT XRD AS PART OF YA-GLASSES CHARACTERIZATION / J. VALÚCHOVÁ	8
THERMAL BEHAVIOR OF YA- GLASS MICROSPHERES / A. PRNOVÁ.....	9
Bi ₂ O ₃ DOPED YTTRIA: A WHITE LIGHT EMISSION FLUORESCENT MATERIAL / P. ŠVANČÁREK...10	
PREPARATION OF A TRANSPARENT YAG CERAMIC / M. MICHÁLKOVÁ.....	11
GRAIN BOUNDARY SEGREGATION AND ANOMALY IN THE SINTERING OF Li-DOPED MgAl ₂ O ₄ / A.TALIMIAN.....	12
UNDERSTANDING THE ROLES OF ADDITIVES IN THE SINTERING OF Y ₂ O ₃ / A. NAJFZADEH.....	13
DYNAMIC TEST AS A METHOD OF CHOICE FOR DETERMINATION OF THE BURST RELEASE OF ZN FROM ZINC DOPED BIOACTIVE GLASS / H. KAŇKOVÁ	14
COPPER-MAGNESIUM CO-SUBSTITUTED MESOPOROUS BIOACTIVE GLASS FOR BONE TISSUE ENGINEERING / A. ANAND	15
THE EFFECT OF ALUMINA INCLUSION WHILE MELTING ON THE STRUCTURE-BIOACTIVITY RELATIONSHIP OF Mg DOPED SILICA-BASED BIOACTIVE GLASSES / O. BASAK.....	16
CRYSTALLIZATION STUDY OF B AND CO CO-DOPED S53P4 BIOACTIVE GLASS FOR BONE TISSUE ENGINEERING APPLICATIONS / E. VARLIK.....	17
POLYMER/BIOACTIVE GLASSES (BGS)/METAL-ORGANIC FRAMEWORKS (MOFS) COMPOSITE SCAFFOLD / N. ALIPANAH.....	18
CORROSION PERFORMANCE AND WEAR RESISTANCE OF LDH REINFORCED SI-HYDROXYAPATITE NANOCOMPOSITE COATING DEPOSITED ON NI-TI ALLOY / R. SAMIEE	19
SINGLE PHASE HIGH-ENTROPY OXIDES: IMPACT OF PARTICLE MORPHOLOGY ON DENSIFICATION AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES / A. CHAUHAN	20
CuWO ₄ /ZIF-8 HYBRID COMPOSITES: PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION / M. IQBAL	21
SE-DOPED BIOACTIVE GLASS/GO/PEEK COMPOSITE COATINGS FOR TI-BASED BIOMEDICAL IMPLANTS / M. ABDOLMALEKI.....	22
NEW MATERIALS IN THE Al ₂ O ₃ -RE ₂ O ₃ SYSTEM WITH INTERESTING OPTICAL PROPERTIES / J. MICHALÍK.....	23
SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF YAG: Eu ²⁺ AND YAG: Eu ³⁺ MICROSPHERES FOR LED APPLICATIONS / M. GHADAMYARI	24
PROCESSING AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF AL ₂ O ₃ /Y ₃ AL ₅ O ₁₂ (YAG)/ZRO ₂ EUTECTIC CERAMICS FABRICATED BY SPARK PLASMA SINTERING / M. VAKHSHOURI.....	25

NEW GLASS-CERAMIC AND CERAMIC MATERIALS WITH INTERESTING MECHANICAL PROPERTIES IN THE SYSTEM $Al_2O_3-La_2O_3-ZrO_2$ / M. BOUJIDA	26
POLYMER DERIVED CERAMIC COATINGS REINFORCED WITH $La_2Zr_2O_7$ POWDER / P. MOGHADDAM.....	27
METHODOLOGY FOR EVALUATION OF CORROSION RESISTANCE IN AZS REFRACTORY MATERIALS DURING THE PRODUCTION OF Ba CRYSTALLINE GLASS / S. KHAN	28
SONO-PHOTO HYBRID CATALYTIC PROCESS FOR THE DEGRADATION OF TETRACYCLINE / M. SAJJADI.....	29

Preparation and study of crystallization kinetics of yttrium-aluminate glasses

A. Akusevich¹, A. Prnová², A. Plško², J. Valúchová², I. Parchovianská¹, M. Parchovianský¹, M. Michálková¹, R. Klement¹

¹FunGlass – Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia (*e-mail: alena.akusevich@tnuni.sk*)

²Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChPT STU, Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

In this work, five compositions of yttrium aluminate glasses (glass microspheres) with a high alumina content were prepared by the Pechini sol-gel method and the flame synthesis method. The behaviour of glasses during crystallization was studied using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD), high-temperature X-ray diffraction analysis (HT-XRD), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

For the sample with the lowest content of Al₂O₃ (70 mol.%), only one exothermic effect was observed. With an increase in the content of aluminium oxide, two exothermic effects appeared in the measured DSC curves of glasses. The temperature gap between the two exothermic effects increases and reaches its maximum value for composition with the highest alumina content (85 mol.%). The XRD patterns measured after DSC analysis revealed the presence of YAG phase and different forms of Al₂O₃ in the samples. The Johnson-Mehl-Avrami-Kolmogorov model (JMAK) were applied to determine the crystallization behavior of the studied system and parameters of JMAK model were obtained. The results indicated predominant three-dimensional and two-dimensional crystals growth.

For all prepared compositions, the hot-press (HP) experiments at a temperature of 1600°C, a pressure of 30 MPa and an isothermal dwell time of 10 min were carried to study the possibility of preparing bulk ceramic materials by sintering of glass microspheres. Fine eutectic microstructures, depending on Al₂O₃ content, were obtained with a good mechanical properties of bulk ceramic materials, the Vickers hardness \approx 16-18 GPa and an indentation fracture toughness \approx 4 MPa m^{1/2}.

Keywords: crystallization kinetics, DSC, JMAK model, yttrium-aluminate glasses.

Acknowledgment:

This work was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under the contract No. APVV-17-0049 and by grant VEGA 1/0476/22.

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

Relationship between photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes and photocatalytic water splitting in oxide and sulfide semiconductors

Michal Žitňan¹, Surjakanta Rana¹, Muhammad Iqbal¹, Vicente D. Rodríguez², Dušan Galusek^{1,3}, Pedro Núñez^{4,5}, José J. Velázquez¹

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin, Studentska 2, 91150 Trencin, Slovakia
(E-mail: michal.zitnan@tnuni.sk)

² Departamento de Física, Universidad de La Laguna, Apto. 456, 38200 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain

³ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChPT STU, Studentska 2, 91150 Trencin, Slovakia

⁴ Departamento de Química, U.D. Química Inorgánica, Universidad de La Laguna, Apto. 456, 38200 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain

⁵ Instituto de Materiales y Nanotecnología, Universidad de La Laguna, Apto. 456, 38200 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain

ABSTRACT

Hydrogen is a renewable and clean energy carrier and one of the most promising alternates for fossil fuels in the future. Currently, the most of hydrogen demands is sourced from steam reforming of natural gas. Alternatively, photo-catalytic water splitting has been considered as one of the most promising approaches for renewable hydrogen production, ever since the discovery of photo-electrochemical water splitting at a TiO₂ electrode.

In addition to TiO₂, another group of ZnCdS-based photocatalysts has emerged, which has the advantage of facile bandgap tuning from 2.55 to 3.6 eV by changing the Zn/Cd ratio. The hydrogen production performance of titanium oxide and zinc-cadmium sulphide was studied by home-built photocatalytic set-up consisting of source of light and hydrogen production reactor located at the focuses of an elliptic cylinder reflector. The response to UV or VIS light can be registered independently. Hydrogen production was monitored continuously using an Omnistar mass spectrometer from Pfeiffer Vacuum Co. connected to the reactor outlet and reached almost 75% of TiO₂ performance.

To be able to compare the photocatalytic effect of samples with adjusted crystallinity or particle size without the Omnistar mass spectrometer, we have developed another photocatalytic reactor at the FunGlass center. In this case the photocatalytic degradation of the organic dyes is employed and studied by UV-VIS spectroscopy. Use of photocatalytic organic dyes degradation process accelerates the selection of candidates for photocatalytic water-splitting.

Keywords: photocatalysis, hydrogen production, dye degradation.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566. This work was also supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under the contract by grant VEGA 1/0844/21.

Spray dry synthesis of FTO beads

O. Sisman¹, M. Michalkova², A. H. Haritha^{1,3}, J. J. Velazquez¹, D. Galusek^{1,2}

¹Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin, 91150 Trencin, Slovakia (orhan.sisman@tnuni.sk)

²Joint Glass Center of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChPT STU, 91150 Trencin, Slovakia

³Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio (CSIC), Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

Transparent conductive oxides (TCOs) are materials that possess optical transparency and high electrical conductivity. They find extensive use in applications requiring simultaneous electrical conduction and light transmission, such as electrochromic windows. TCOs can be coated onto glass to create low-emissivity (low-e) windows that reflect infrared radiation and absorb ultraviolet radiation, thus reducing radiant heat loss and minimizing exposure to harmful UV rays. Fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO), one of the well-known TCO, is a wide bandgap semiconductor material that exhibits optical transmittance in the visible region. FTO glasses, with their combination of high conductivity and transparency, are crucial for enabling electrical contacts without obstructing light transmission, thus facilitating the development of advanced electronic devices.

In this study, we synthesized spherical FTO beads as functional substrates for growing nanomaterials. Spherical surfaces offer several advantages such as flexibility, thermal and chemical stability, and a 3D structure compared to flat substrates. Using FTO beads for nanomaterial growth can effectively support surface functionality and cost efficiency in a wide range of applications. The FTO beads were fabricated using a spray dryer, and two different sol-gel precursor solutions were prepared as feed solutions. The spray drying parameters, feeding rate, and inlet temperatures were kept consistent for both solutions. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images revealed distinct bead formation, while X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) measurements confirmed the enhanced crystallinity of FTO beads at higher annealing temperatures. These preliminary results show promise for designing 3D FTO substrates and functional materials.

Keywords: Functional glass, spherical glass, spray drying method, transparent conductive oxide (TCO).

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

This work was also supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under the contract by grant VEGA 1/0844/21.

Innovative functionalities of ion-exchanged glasses

Rajesh Dagupati¹, Ali Talimian¹, Dušan Galusek^{1,2}

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovak Republic

² Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChPT STU, Trencin, Slovak Republic

(E-mail: rajesh.dagupati@tnuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

Although ion-exchange processes have been extensively investigated to improve the mechanical properties of glasses in recent years, little attention has been given to introducing new functionalities to glass and glass ceramics via ion exchange. In the present work, the use of ion-exchange processes for introducing new functionalities to glasses and glass ceramics is reviewed. A case study is presented to demonstrate how the production of a surface layer with the “*forbidden glass structure*” by ion exchange gives new functionalities to conventional glasses.

Keywords: Glass, Ion-exchange, Luminescence

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of the dissemination activities of project FunGlass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 739566. Financial support of this work by the grants VEGA 2/0028/21 and APVV 0019-10 is gratefully acknowledged. This work has also been supported by the Research Agency of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic, by the project: Advancement and support of R&D for "Centre for diagnostics and quality testing of materials" in the domains of the RIS3 SK specialization, Acronym: CEDITEK II., ITMS2014+ code 313011W442.

Growth of ZIF-8 on 3D printed ceramic alumina structure for gas separation application

Surjyakanta Rana¹, Roman Sajzew², Oksana Smirnova², Josef Bernd Slowik², Jose J. Velazquez¹, Alexander Knebel², Dušan Galusek¹, Lothar Wondraczek²

¹Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trenčín, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia. (Email: Surjyakanta.rana@tnuni.sk)

²Otto Schott Institute of Materials Research, Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena, 07743 Jena, Germany

ABSTRACT

A subfamily of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) known as zeolitic imidazolate frameworks (ZIFs) is made up of tetrahedrally coordinated metal nodes that are linked by imidazolate ligands [1]. ZIFs (zeolites and MOFs) combine the benefits of two families and have demonstrated combinatory material features, such as thermal and/or chemical stability, and particularly very small pores that enable molecular sieving [2-4]. ZIF-8, for instance, exhibits considerable gas separation capabilities in the form of ZIF-8 thin film membranes and is an effective adsorbent material for capturing and/or eliminating extremely poisonous or hazardous compounds by physical and/or chemical adsorption processes. Moreover, combining these materials with rapid prototyping by means of additive manufacturing enables the development of 3D structures with precise form control and the usage of innovative membrane and module geometries.

The research conducted last year at Otto Schott Institute of Materials Research in Jena was focused on (i) the growth of ZIF-8 on various architectures of 3D-printed ceramic tubular membranes that allow to create double helical DNA-inspired channels inside of the mentioned tubular membranes and (ii) Investigating the effects of material characteristics (such as porosity, metal-support-linker interaction, and growth of ZIFs based on different sides of the 3D printed materials).

Moreover, to enable the targeted creation of materials that significantly increase the efficiency and specific selectivity in gas separation, a key factor is the interaction phenomena between the surface of the 3D printed support structure and the grown films. In this sense, we are presenting concepts for 3D-printed ceramic alumina-based MOF membranes and the results obtained by different characterization techniques demonstrate that the ZIF-8 was successfully fabricated on the 3D-printed ceramic scaffold. Further discussion may lead to the development of MOF membrane science and supported MOF film technology on ceramic alumina supports [5].

Keywords: 3D printing, ZIF-8 membranes, Hydrothermal synthesis, Gas separation.

References:

- [1] B. Hosseinimonjezi, S. Okur, R. Limbach, A. Chandresh, K. Sen, T. Hashem, M. Schwotzer, L. Wondraczek, C. Wöll, A. Knebel, *ACS Nano*, 2023, 17, 6121 - 6130.
- [2] H.T. Kwon, H. Jeong, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2013, 135, 10763 - 10768.
- [3] A. Imtiaz, M. H. D. Othman, A. Jilani, I. U. Khan, R. Kamaludin, O. Samue, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.*, 2022, 10, 108541.
- [4] A. Schejn, L. Balan, V. Falk, L. Aranda, G. Medjahdi, R. Schneider, *Cryst. Eng. Comm.*, 2014, 16, 4493 - 4500.
- [5] B. Hosseinimonjezi, K. Kutonova, M. Tsotsalas, S. Henke, A. Knebel, *Angew. Chem. Int Ed.*, 2020, 60, 28, 15153 - 15164.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project FunGlass.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

HT XRD as part of YA-glasses characterization

**J. Valúchová¹, A. Prnová¹, M. Parchovianský², P. Švančárek², B. Pecušová², B. Hruška²,
R. Klement², D. Galusek^{1,2}**

¹ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 91150 Trenčín, Slovakia

² Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 91150 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

To successfully control the crystallization of glasses and to adjust their sintering conditions, it is necessary to know their thermal behaviour. As materials often exhibit phase changes during heat treatment, which then influence further processing, a combination of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) to investigate the thermal behaviour of materials and XRD powder diffraction and high temperature XRD (HT XRD) analysis is often used to study these changes.

During HT XRD powder diffraction analysis, the XRD recording of the sample is first measured at laboratory temperature over the widest possible range of 2θ angles. Subsequently, the sample is heated at a defined heating rate over the desired temperature interval, and a short XRD scan is measured at every temperature step, e.g. every 10 °C. The short measurement is only performed in the 2θ interval, in which the expected phase changes can be monitored. The sample is then cooled down to the room temperature and another a second long measurement is recorded. Such attitude complements a DSC analysis and helps to elucidate any crystallization effects observed in the DSC records of the measured systems.

Four glass samples in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$ system were prepared using the sol-gel method and flame synthesis. The composition of the prepared glasses was derived from the eutectic composition of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ system (76.8 mol.% of Al_2O_3 and 23.2 mol.% of Y_2O_3), where 5 and 10 mol.% of Al_2O_3 in the AYZr1 and AYZr2 samples were replaced with ZrO_2 , and 5 and 10 mol.% of Y_2O_3 were replaced with ZrO_2 in the AYZr3 and AYZr4 samples.

All samples have similar thermal properties, with the presence of three exothermic effects in the DSC records. The crystallization takes place over a wide temperature range 933-1160 °C. In the DSC record of the AYZr4 sample, a single exothermic effect was observed with the onset at 937 °C and the crystallization is observed over a narrow temperature interval 937-951 °C. The diffraction records after the DSC analysis contained yttrium aluminum garnet as the main phase, monoclinic and tetragonal forms of zirconium oxide, and traces of $\theta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. The exothermic effects can be attributed to the crystallization of the phases mentioned above. The crystallization was investigated in more detail by HT X-ray powder diffraction analysis in the temperature interval 25-1200 °C: monoclinic ZrO_2 crystallized first. The temperature interval of crystallization for each composition differed. The tetragonal to monoclinic phase transformation of ZrO_2 was recorded in the same temperature interval, 1080-1200 °C, for all compositions. Crystallization of YAG was documented in the interval 930 - 1200 °C, with the onset being different for each studied composition.

Keywords: $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$, DSC, XRD, HT XRD, SEM

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

Thermal behavior of YA- glass microspheres

**A. Prnová¹, J. Valúchová¹, B. Pecušová², M. Majerová³, A. Akusevich², R. Klement²,
D. Galusek²**

¹ Vitrum Laugaricio – Joint Glass Center of The IIC SAS, TnU AD and FCHPT STU, Študentska 2, SK-911 50
Trenčín, Slovak Republic

anna.prnova@tnuni.sk

²Centre for functional and surface functionalized glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentska 2,
SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovak Republic

³Department of Magnetometry, Institute of Measurement Science, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská cesta
9, SK-842 19 Bratislava, Slovak Republic

ABSTRACT

Yttrium aluminate (YA) glasses and their crystalline counterparts belong to a new generation of materials for high-temperature applications, as they can maintain their interesting mechanical properties and corrosion resistance even at high working temperatures of up to 1300°C. However, a price for these properties is the technological and financial complexity of their preparation. One of the possibilities for preparing larger pieces of these materials is flame synthesis of glass microspheres and their subsequent viscous or diffusion flow sintering. An important condition for the successful application of this procedure is a thorough examination of the thermal behavior of YA glasses. The use of thermal analyzes has become almost routine nowadays. The results of these analyzes are often supplemented by HT X-ray powder diffraction, SEM and TEM techniques. An interesting solution is also offered by the combination of non-isothermal and isothermal TA analyzes in combination with crystallization experiments. In this work, we used the STA analyzer in DTA/TG mode in combination with SEM, and X-ray powder diffraction analysis to investigate the temperature behavior of three compositions of glass in the system $Y_2O_3-Al_2O_3$ and to identify thermal effects associated with crystallization in the temperature interval 850-1100°C. A simultaneous crystallization of YAG and $\theta - Al_2O_3$ phase was observed, while the course of individual events was dependent on the Al_2O_3 content in the samples. The results will be used in the design of heat treatment programs for HP sintering.

Keywords: YA glass microspheres, DTA/TG analysis

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566. The financial support of this work by the project APVV 19-0010 and the project Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass (CEGLASS), operational program Research and innovation, co-funded from European Regional Development Fund, ITMS code 313011R453 is gratefully acknowledged.

Bi₂O₃ doped yttria: A white light emission fluorescent material

P. Švančárek¹, R. Klement² and D. Galusek^{1,2}

¹ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, FunGlass, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: peter.svancarek@tnuni.sk)

² Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trenčín, 911 50

Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

The Y₂O₃ ceramic materials doped by 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4 at.% of Bi³⁺ were prepared and influence of the amount of additive on fluorescence properties was investigated.

SEM revealed that sintered samples are very porous. EDXS and EBSD analysis have shown that in the matrix of cubic Y₂O₃ there is dispersed the cubic phase tentatively identified as BiYO₃. It is not possible to identify these cubic phases using the EBSD only, because the lattice parameters are very similar. Outside of BiYO₃ grains the concentration of bismuth is under the detection limit of EDXS detector.

All prepared Y₂O₃:Bi³⁺ ceramic materials have shown a broad emission band in visible part of electromagnetic spectra centred at 500nm(green) with smaller shouldered band at about 415nm (blue) when irradiated by UV radiation of 330nm wavelength. The strongest intensity of luminescence was observed for materials doped by 0.5 at.% of Bi³⁺. Further rise of dopant concentration caused dropping of the PL intensity.

Both blue and green emissions can be explained by ¹S₀→³P₁ Bi³⁺ transition when Bi³⁺ ion is in the C₂ (blue) and S₆(green) site.

Keywords: Bi₂O₃-Y₂O₃ ceramics, EBSD, EDXS, Fluorescence, cold white light

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

Preparation of a transparent YAG ceramic

M. Micháľková¹, I. Sokolov², T. Spusta², K. Maca², J. Kraxner³, Dušan Galusek^{1,3}

¹ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, FunGlass, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: monika.michalkova@tnuni.sk)

² CEITEC BUT, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123, Brno, Czech Republic

³ FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Transparent ceramic materials are commonly recognized as the next generation of solid-state lasers, owing to their unique advantages such as better uniformity, short production period, ease in technology, and flexibility in large-sized production, compared with their single crystal counterparts. Transparent yttrium aluminium garnet (YAG) ceramic is the most widely adopted solid-state laser gain medium due to its high transparency, high melting point, and excellent mechanical and chemical properties [1].

There are two basic ways for the preparation of transparent YAG: i) sintering of YAG powder (synthesized e.g. by co-precipitation, sol-gel method, or combustion synthesis), ii) reaction sintering of a mixture of Y_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 powders. The third innovative possibility presents the sintering of already densified glass in YAG composition and its crystallization at higher temperatures.

The main goal of the proposed work was to prepare transparent polycrystalline YAG with at least one of the mentioned methods and to compare them in relation to the optical properties of obtained ceramics.

YAG powders were synthesized by combustion synthesis, sol-gel Pechini method, and radiation-induced synthesis. Suspension properties were optimized for all these powders as well as for a mixture of yttria-alumina powders for reactive sintering. After slip casting into a silicon mould and subsequent drying, samples undergo the burnout of dispersant residues.

Final sintering was performed at 1735°C for 10 h in a vacuum with subsequent annealing in the air atmosphere at 1100 °C for 80 hours to eliminate oxygen vacancies. The same sintering regime was applied to the sample prepared in an amorphous state previously densified by SPS at $T=912^\circ\text{C}$.

Results (**Fig. 1**) show the sample with the highest optical quality prepared by reaction sintering.

Reference:

[1] Wen, Lei, et al. "Synthesis of nanocrystalline yttria powder and fabrication of transparent YAG ceramics." *Journal of the European Ceramic Society* 24.9 (2004): 2681-2688.

Keywords: alumina, reaction sintering, suspension, YAG, yttria,

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of the dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566. Financial support of this work by the grant VEGA 2 1/0456/20s is gratefully acknowledged.

Grain Boundary Segregation and Anomaly in the Sintering of Li-doped $MgAl_2O_4$

Ali Talimian¹, Václav Pouchlý^{2,3}, Róbert Klement¹, Ana M. Betlrán⁴, Karel Maca^{2,3}, Dušan Galusek^{1,5}

¹ Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalised Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 91150 Trenčín, Slovakia (Email: ali.talimian@tnuni.sk)

² Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkyňova 123, 612 00 Brno, the Czech Republic

³ Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Brno University of Technology, Technická 2, 612 00 Brno, the Czech Republic

⁴ Departamento de Ingeniería y Ciencia de los Materiales y del Transporte, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería, Universidad de Sevilla, 41092, Sevilla, Spain

⁵ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 91150 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Various sintering aids have been used to improve mass transport and promote the densification of magnesium aluminate spinel; however, grain growth is inevitable when mass transport is accelerated. The present work investigates how doping with lithium ions suppresses grain growth while promoting the densification of spinel. The incorporation of lithium ions into the spinel structure changes the defects concentration and promotes mass transport. Structural and microstructural studies revealed that grain boundary complexation and the segregation of secondary phases, such as $LiAlO_2$ and MgO , at the grain boundary of spinel can prevent grain growth. A thermodynamic model was employed to explain and predict the critical concentration of lithium at which grain boundary segregation occurs. The results of this study corroborated the previously reported grain growth anomaly in Li-doped spinel.

Keywords: Sintering, Grain Boundary, Segregation

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of the dissemination activities of project FunGlass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 739566. Financial support of this work by the grants GAČR 20-14237S, MŠMT LTT18013 (Inter-Transfer), VEGA 2/0028/21 and APVV 0019-10 is gratefully acknowledged.

Understanding the Roles of Additives in the Sintering of Y_2O_3

**A. Najafzadeh¹, A. Talimian², V. Girman^{3,4}, R. Sedlák³, R. Poyato⁵, Pavol Hvizdoš³,
Karel Maca^{6,7}, Dušan Galusek^{1,2}**

¹ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChFT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovak Republic

(ali.najafzadeh@tnuni.sk)

² FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovak Republic

³ Institute of Materials Research of SAS, Watsonova 47, 040 01, Kosice, Slovakia

⁴ Faculty of Science, Pavol Jozef Safarik University, Park Angelinum 9, 040 01 Košice, Slovak Republic

⁵ Inst. Ciencia de Materiales de Sevilla, ICMS, CSIC-Universidad de Sevilla, Américo Vespucio 49, 41092, Sevilla, Spain

⁶ CEITEC BUT, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123, 612 00 Brno, Czech Republic

⁷ Institute of Materials Science and Engineering, Brno University of Technology, Technická 2, 616 69 Brno, Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

In the present work, we revisit the role of sintering additives in the densification and grain growth of yttrium oxide. Dense Y_2O_3 bodies, with a relative density $> 98.5\%$, were produced from commercial yttrium oxide nanopowder following two approaches: (i) activated sintering and (ii) liquid phase sintering.

The activated sintering was performed by doping the commercial powder with transition metal ions; the results showed that the electronic structure and ionicity of doping cations determine their impact on defect chemistry, critical concentration, and sintering behavior of doped Y_2O_3 .

Liquid phase sintering was carried out using limited amounts of Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 , up to 1 wt.%, as sintering additives producing a liquid phase by reacting with Y_2O_3 at high temperatures. The addition of the sintering aids lowered the sintering temperature and suppressed grain growth. The changes in the solid-liquid interfacial energy due to the precipitation of yttrium-silicate/yttrium-aluminate at the grain boundaries are responsible for the grain growth suppression during liquid phase sintering.

Keywords: Additives; Grain growth; Liquid phase sintering; Y_2O_3 .

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

This research work has also been supported by the Research Agency of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic, by the project: Advancement and support of R&D for "Centre for diagnostics and quality testing of materials" in the domains of the RIS3 SK specialization, Acronym: CEDITEK II., ITMS2014+ code 313011W442.

Dynamic test as a method of choice for determination of the burst release of Zn from zinc doped bioactive glass

H. Kaňková¹, L. Buňová¹, M. Michálek¹, D. Galusková¹

¹ FunGlass, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: hana.kankova@tnuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

Zinc doped bioactive glass prepared by conventional melting was tested in simulated body fluid (SBF) to quantitatively determine zinc ion release at the early stage of dissolution of bioactive glass. The analysis of the leaching solution was performed in a flow-through arrangement, with the reaction cell connected directly to the nebulizer of the ICP OES. The dynamic flow through tests were performed using various flow rates and the effect of flow rate on dissolution was discussed. Possible formation of zinc mineral phases as alteration products precipitating from SBF solution along with hydroxyapatite was evaluated using the PHREEQC modelling code.

Keywords: zinc doped glass, dissolution, SBF solution

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566. The authors would like to acknowledge VEGA 01/0191/20 grant.

Copper-magnesium co-substituted mesoporous bioactive glass for bone tissue engineering

Akrity Anand^{1,2}, **Dušan Galusek**¹, **Aldo R. Boccaccini**², **Dagmar Galusková**¹

¹ Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, TnUAD, 911 01 Trenčín, Slovakia

² Institute of Biomaterials, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany
(e-mail: akrity.anand@tnuni.sk)

Abstract

Mesoporous bioactive glasses (MBG) are vastly investigated materials to repair, restore and regenerate osseous tissues owing to its bioactivity, nontoxic, biodegradability properties. The biological activities of MBG can be customized by adding therapeutics ions such as copper (Cu) and magnesium (Mg). The addition of therapeutics in MBG can provide more functionalities such as angiogenesis, osteogenesis and antibacterial characteristics. In this contribution Cu and Mg co-doped (1:1 ratio) MBG with nominal glass composition of $80\text{SiO}_2-(15-2x)\text{CaO}-5\text{P}_2\text{O}_5-x\text{CuO}-x\text{MgO}$ ($x=0.5, 1$ and 2 mol%), was prepared by sol-gel based evaporation induced self-assembly technique (EISA).

The compositional analysis of co-doped system characterized by ICP-OES techniques which confirmed the presence of dopant ions in requisite amount, although the amount of P_2O_5 was lower (<0.5 mol. %) for all the prepared glasses in respect of nominal compositions. XRD confirms the amorphous phase of glass while BET confirms the formation of high surface area for co-doped powders (~ 319 m^2/g) in contrast to control glass (~ 253 m^2/g).

All the MBGs powder showed apatite formation when immersed in simulated body fluid (SBF). XRD results confirms the formation of hydroxyapatite (HAp) layer on the surfaces of MBG after 7 days, while SEM images showed initiation of the formation of apatite after 1 day of soaking. The ionic extract of co-doped powders were cultured with MC3T3-E1 preosteoblast cells and normal human dermal fibroblast cells (NHDF). Both cells showed viability above 50% at MBG extract concentrations of 1 wt./vol.% or lower. For antibacterial result with sequential increase in Cu concentration the zone of inhibition for the bacteria is more prominent.

In conclusion, the co-doping of MBG powder (up to 2mol.%) showed improved bioactivity, biocompatibility and antibacterial effect and could be considered as promising materials for bone tissue regeneration applications.

Keywords: bioactive glass, hydroxyapatite, osteoblast cells

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

The Effect of Alumina Inclusion While Melting on the Structure-Bioactivity Relationship of Mg Doped Silica-Based Bioactive Glasses

Onat Basak¹, Martin Michálek² and Mária Chromčíková^{1,3}

¹ VILA, FunGlass, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: onat.basak@tnuni.sk)

² Biomaterials, FunGlass, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

³ VILA – Joined Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Platinum crucibles are commonly used in the melting of glass. However, they are expensive and pose possible health risks due to immersion in hydrofluoric acid (HF) during the cleaning procedure. Additionally, phosphate presence may cause platinum crucible corrosion [1]. Although alumina crucibles are less expensive than platinum crucibles, they promote inclusions into the glass melt by diffusion [1]. Since alumina inhibits the development of hydroxyapatite (HA), alumina crucibles are rarely used for melting bioactive glasses [2]. Nevertheless, it has been demonstrated that Al₂O₃ does not inhibit HA production, and osteosarcoma cell proliferation on the bioactive glass surface was observed up to 1.5 mol% [2]. Al₂O₃ also reduces the crystallization tendency and increases the thermal stability of glasses [3].

Magnesium is the fourth most abundant element in the human body and has long been known to promote osteoblast formation [4]. Furthermore, because Mg²⁺ ions have a stronger field than Ca²⁺ ions, MgO decreases the crystallization tendencies of bioactive glasses, and SEM pictures revealed that a half-substitution of MgO/CaO for Bioglass® 45S5 resulted in strongly sintered particles [5].

The impact of alumina diffusion on the structure-bioactivity relationship of the bioactive glasses was investigated in this work. Raman, MAS-NMR, and DTA techniques were used to achieve this goal. Bioactivity studies were performed in predetermined amounts of simulated bodily fluid (SBF) at 37 °C. The formation of HA was studied using XRD, SEM, and FTIR. Glass dissolving is also investigated via ion release from ion-coupled plasma (ICP).

Keywords: Alumina crucible, bioactivity, crystallization resistance, dissolution thermal stability, silicate glass structure

References

- [1] N. Sawangboon et al., International Journal of Applied Glass Science, 2020, 11(1), 46–57.
- [2] H. Tripathi, C. Rath, A. S. Kumar, P. P. Manna, and S. P. Singh; Materials Science and Engineering C, 2019, 94, 279–290.
- [3] K. Dimitriadis, D. U. Tulyaganov, and S. Agathopoulos; Journal of the European Ceramic Society, 2021, 41(1), 929–940.
- [4] I. Cacciotti, A. Bianco, M. Lombardi, and L. Montanaro; Journal of the European Ceramic Society, 2009, 29(14), 2969–2978.
- [5] R. Wetzell, M. Blochberger, F. Scheffler, L. Hupa, and D.S. Brauer; Scientific Reports, 2020, 10(1), 1–10.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566 and was supported by The Slovak Grant Agency for Science under Grant No. VEGA 2/0091/20, and APVV-21-0016.

Crystallization study of B and Co co-doped S53P4 bioactive glass for bone tissue engineering applications

E. Varlik¹, N. Mutlu¹, F. Kurtuldu¹, S. Chen¹, A. R. Boccaccini², and M. Michálek¹

¹ Department of Biomaterials, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

² Institute of Biomaterials, Department of Material Science and Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, Cauerstr. 6, 91058, Erlangen, Germany

(E-mail: ertugrul.varlik@tuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

The thermal treatment applied to bioactive glasses (BGs) directly affects several important properties, including microstructure, crystallinity, mechanical properties, and biological response. Bioactive glasses, similar composition to 45S5 Bioglass[®] (silicate-based), are prone to crystallize readily in elevated temperatures. The primary idea of this study was to understand the crystallization behavior of the co-substituted silicate-based bioactive glass system utilized in the scaffolds for bone tissue engineering applications. The B and Co co-substituted S53P4 SiO₂-Na₂O-CaO-P₂O₅ bioactive glass systems were fabricated by a conventional glass melting route. High-Temperature X-Ray Diffraction (HT-XRD), Differential Scanning Calorimetry/Thermogravimetry (DSC/TG), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) with Energy Dispersive X-Ray Analysis (EDX), and Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) were utilized to justify the fidelity of the system for scaffold fabrication. When thermal processes are conducted at temperatures surpassing the crystallization onset, the amorphous phases within the structure of BGs undergo an undesired transformation into crystalline forms. This structural change negatively impacts the efficacy of the ions released from the glass, thereby impeding their biological activity. Both heat-treated and non-heat-treated co-substituted S53P4 BG powders (particle size <40 μm) were subjected to *in-vitro* Simulated Body Fluid (SBF) solution for various periods (24h, 72h, 1, and 2 weeks) to confirm the hydroxyapatite-like crystal formation. The powders were examined after immersion to SBF using SEM, XRD, and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) for the *in-vitro* bioactivity.

Keywords: Bioactive glasses, Bone tissue engineering, Crystallization behavior, Melt-derived

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

Polymer/bioactive glasses (BGs)/metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) composite scaffold

N. Alipanah¹, O. Sisman¹, M. Michálek¹, L. Wondraczek^{2,3}, A. R. Boccaccini⁴, D. Galusek⁵ and Z. Neščáková¹

¹FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

²Otto Schott Institute of Materials Research, Friedrich Schiller University Jena, 07743 Jena, Germany

³Center of Energy and Environmental Chemistry - CEEC Jena, University of Jena, 07743 Jena, Germany

⁴Institute of Biomaterials, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, 91058, Erlangen, Germany

⁵Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChFT STU, 91150, Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: nariman.alipanah@tnuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

Tissue engineering holds immense promise for regenerating damaged tissues, particularly in the field of bone tissue engineering. The objective of this study is to develop a novel composite scaffold, referred to as composite bioreactors, by combining polymer, bioactive glasses (BGs), and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), in order to achieve osteogenesis and durable antimicrobial properties throughout the entire period. To fulfill this purpose, a polymer/bioactive glass composite that closely resembles the structure of natural bone will be designed. Bioactive glasses will induce osteogenesis and facilitate the integration of the scaffold with existing bone tissue. Additionally, gelatin, a natural polymer that mimics the extracellular matrix (ECM) of natural bone, will serve as a carrier for antimicrobial agents. Although bioactive glasses have shown potential in stimulating bone regeneration, incorporating effective antimicrobial properties into such scaffolds has proven challenging. To address this challenge, the incorporation of nano-porous MOFs into a gelatin polymer matrix is proposed. Certain MOFs consisting of therapeutic ions have exhibited significant antimicrobial effects in biocidal solutions. MOFs, also known for their highly ordered structures and controlled release capabilities, offer an ideal solution for imparting durable antimicrobial activity to the scaffold. These materials can gradually release therapeutic ions to provide sustainable antimicrobial effects and cover the patient with medication for a longer time period. The project involves synthesizing crystalline MOFs structures based on ZIF-8 by hydrothermal process. Physico-chemical characterization of this material and evaluating of possible cytotoxicity *in vitro* will be performed. Further optimizing of the scaffold fabrication process to ensure proper distribution of MOFs and BGs within the gelatin matrix will be done. The efficacy of the scaffold will be evaluated through *in vitro* studies, including antimicrobial activity tests, biocompatibility assessments, and analysis of release of therapeutic ions from the MOFs/BGs. The successful implementation of these composite scaffolds could revolutionize bone tissue engineering strategies, offering improved treatment options for bone defects and infections.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing, Antimicrobial properties, Bioactive glasses, Bone tissue engineering, MOFs

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

Corrosion performance and wear resistance of LDH reinforced Si-hydroxyapatite nanocomposite coating deposited on Ni-Ti alloy

R. Samiee¹, A. Duran², Y. Castro², and A. H. Pakseresht¹

¹ Department of Coating Processes, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: reza.samiee@tnuni.sk)

² Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio (CSIC), Campus de Cantoblanco, 28049, Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

The replacement of bone tissue for metallic implants has gained special interest in the last decades. However, there are implant that suffer corrosion, fatigue fracture, wear and incompatibility with host tissue, aspects that can be solved by superficial modification of the metallic substrates [1]. Particularly, inorganic ceramic coatings such as hydroxyapatite (HAp, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) have been widely employed to improve the incompatibility [2]. Nevertheless, the brittle nature and poor strength of HAp coating are a problem, especially when the implant need to work under load-bearing conditions. Therefore, the incorporation of nanoparticles as secondary bioactive fillers enhance their characteristics [3].

Thus, this work is based on the preparation of Sr/Ga nanoparticles by LDH and their incorporation in silicon substituted HAp coating as an active/passive filler. The nanoparticles would act as drug/ion release to increase the bioactivity and also to block the corrosive species and avoid the corrosion of the metallic substrate. For this purpose, Sr/Ga LDH nanoparticles has been synthesized using co-precipitation and ion exchange method. Then, surface of Ti substrates has been pre-treated by anodizing to increase the corrosion resistance and adhesion properties. The morphology, topology, composition, and electrochemical properties of the passivated surfaces have been characterized.

Finally, a Si-HAp coating loaded with Sr/Ga LDH nanoparticles has been electrophoretically deposited on anodized samples. The release ability of LDHs make them a desirable candidate as bioactive additive for bone regeneration. The flake morphology of these nanoparticles can enhance the barrier performance and the toughness of the HAp coating [4]. The effect of LDH incorporation on the anticorrosion behavior of Si-HAp coated nitinol samples was studied by polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). The lowest amount of nickel release was observed for LDH @ Si-HAp coated nitinol samples.

Keywords: Nitinol, Hydroxyapatite, Layered double hydroxide, surface modification, Corrosion, anodization.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

References:

- [1] S. Awasthi, S. K. Pandey, E. Arunan, & C. Srivastava *Journal of Materials Chemistry B*, **2021**, 9, 228-249.
- [2] A. Mehrvarz, Y. Ghazanfar-Ahari, J. Khalil-Allafi, S. Mahdavi, & M. Etminanfar *Ceramics International*, **2016**, 48, 2191-2202.
- [3] V. Khalili, J. Khalil-Allafi, W. Xia, A. B. Parsa, J. Frenzel, C. Somsen, & G. Eggeler, *Applied Surface Science*, **2016**, 366, 158-165.
- [4] A. Chatterjee, P. Bharadiya, & D. Hansora *Applied Clay Science*, **2019**, 177, 19-36.

Single phase high-entropy oxides: impact of particle morphology on densification and optical properties

Avnee Chauhan¹, Dušan Galusek^{1,2}

¹ Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: avnee.chauhan@tuni.sk)

²Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

A new class of ceramics, known as high-entropy oxides (HEOs), has generated considerable research interest because of their novel intrinsic properties and significant potential for application in various fields. The HEO concept provides access to unexplored regions in the multi-element phase diagram. Due to their wide bandgap, rare earth oxides with high entropy are considered to be potential materials for applications such as laser hosts, scintillating devices, multi-wavelength phosphors, and luminescence materials. This work describes the single-phase synthesis of a multicomponent rare earth system mixed in an equimolar ratio containing combinations of CeO₂, La₂O₃, Sm₂O₃, Pr₂O₃, Y₂O₃, and Dy₂O₃. In this study, a novel high-entropy ceramic phosphor with the composition (Y_{0.2}Ce_{0.2}Dy_{0.2}Sm_{0.2}La_{0.2}) O_{2-δ} was successfully prepared using solid-state sintering and combustion synthesis techniques. The change in the synthesis process resulted in particles with varying morphologies which had a direct impact on the densification of sintered samples. It is crucial to understand that the densification of the samples can significantly affect the transparency of the material. X-ray powder diffraction and scanning electron microscopy were applied to analyze the phase composition and microstructures of the as-prepared powders and sintered ceramics. The luminescent properties of the bulk ceramic sample were also determined, and multi-excitation and emission spectra were measured. Strong emissions originating from Dy³⁺ and Sm³⁺ were observed at 572nm, 612nm, and 654nm. The emission color was effectively regulated under multi-wavelength excitation, yielding a photoluminescence performance. The high-entropy (Y_{0.2}Ce_{0.2}Dy_{0.2}Sm_{0.2}La_{0.2}) O_{2-δ} ceramic can be considered as a novel material for white light application with multi-wavelength excitation and tunable emission.

Keywords: Configurational entropy, Functional ceramics, High-entropy ceramic, Photoluminescence.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

CuWO₄/ZIF-8 hybrid composites: Preparation and characterization

M. U. Iqbal¹, M. Zitnan¹, L. Wondraczek², D. Galusek^{1,3}, J.J. Velazquez¹

¹Functional Materials, Centre for functional and surface functionalized glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

²Otto-Scott Institute for Material Research, Friedrich Schiller University, Jena, Germany

³Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChPT STU, Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: muhammad.iqbal@tuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

CuWO₄, as a semiconductor-based photocatalyst with a moderate bandgap (2.2–2.4 eV), has been attracting considerable attention as a promising candidate for H₂ generation. Despite that, CuWO₄ does not show significant improvements in photocatalysis for hydrogen evolution reaction. Thus, to enhance the photocatalytic performance, CuWO₄ was modified with ZIF-8 creating a heterojunction-based material that increase the surface area, broaden their light absorption region, inhibit the recombination of photogenerated electrons to these semiconductors, improving its electron transfer kinetics and properties [1]. CuWO₄/ZIF-8 hybrid composites were prepared by co-precipitation method followed by the in situ-growth method. The successful synthesis of ZIF-8/CuWO₄ hybrid structures were confirmed by SEM, XRD, FTIR, and XPS. Moreover, the as-synthesized composites contain both CuWO₄ and ZIF-8 phases. Due to this, the band gap of the material was reduced from 5.22 to 3.5 eV, as confirmed by DRS-UV-Vis spectroscopy. The ideal band gap of photocatalyst lies in between 2 to 3.5 eV for the effective absorption of light spectra and subsequent water splitting. In this sense, the obtained 1:1 CuWO₄/ZIF-8 hybrid structures heterojunction show a band gap of 3.5 eV, similar that is required for water splitting. Also, the PL intensity for 1:1 CuWO₄/ZIF-8 was lowered as compared to CuWO₄ and ZIF-8 alone. So, the heterojunction between CuWO₄ and ZIF-8 reduced the carrier recombination. It is expected to improve the photocatalytic activity of 1:1 CuWO₄/ZIF-8 hybrid structures.

Keywords: Heterojunction, Hydrogen Evolution Reaction, Metal organic Frameworks (MOFs)

Fig. Mechanism of Photocatalysis in the CuWO₄/ZIF-8 heterojunction

References:

[1] N. Jatav, J. Kuntail, D. Khan, A. Kumar De, and I. Sinha, J Colloid Interface Sci 2021, 599, 717–729.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

This project has received funding from the FunGlass PHD grant no. 22_05 and VEGA 1-0844-21.

Se-doped Bioactive Glass/GO/PEEK composite coatings for Ti-based biomedical implants

M. Abdolmaleki¹, G.A. Clavijo-Mejía¹, A. R. Boccaccini² and M. Michálek¹

¹FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

²Institute of Biomaterials, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, 91058, Erlangen, Germany
(E-mail: mina.abdolmaleki@tnuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

Biomedical implant performance relies on the tissue-implant interface, wherein coatings play a crucial role by providing biocompatibility, bioactivity, and additional features such as anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties to address prosthetic infections. This study aims to develop a durable coating system for titanium-based implants in hard tissue applications, combining Selenium-doped (Se-doped) bioactive glasses, functionalized graphene oxide (GO), and polyether ether ketone (PEEK) polymer. Bioactive glasses (BGs) coatings are preferred in bone tissue engineering due to their controlled biodegradability, ability to bond with soft and hard tissues, formation of a hydroxycarbonate apatite (HCA) layer upon contact with physiological fluids, and capacity to enhance cellular adhesion, osteoblast proliferation, and differentiation. Se-doped BGs also exhibit effectiveness in apoptosis in cancer cells, bone regeneration, and drug delivery for bone tissue therapy. Furthermore, graphene oxide (GO) can act as a container decorated with therapeutic ions to improve the antibacterial properties, biocompatibility, and corrosion resistance of the coating while controlling the release of therapeutic ions for durable properties [1,2]. Plasma treatment of the implants will be envisaged to enhance coating adhesion to the titanium substrate, its surface functionalization, and overall help the electrophoretic deposition (EPD) method achieve a uniform layer [3,4]. Finally, the mechanical, antimicrobial, and biocompatibility properties of the coatings will be evaluated, contributing to the development of advanced coatings that overcome the limitations of current surface modification techniques, address infections, and enhance patient outcomes in biomedical applications.

Keywords: Coating, Bioactive Glass, Graphene Oxide, plasma treatment, EPD

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

References

- [1] B. Karakuzu-İkizler, P. Terzioğlu, B.S. Oduncu-Tekerek, S. Yücel, Effect of selenium incorporation on the structure and in vitro bioactivity of 45S5 bioglass, *J. Aust. Ceram. Soc.* 56 (2020) 697–709.
- [2] K. Ravichandran, I.J. SA, N. Manivannan, M. ali Badusha, T.S.N.S. Narayanan, Engineering the surface of titanium to improve its bioactivity and antibacterial activity through a multi-functional coating approach, *New J. Chem.* (2023).
- [3] X. Sheng, A. Wang, Z. Wang, H. Liu, J. Wang, C. Li, Advanced Surface Modification for 3D-Printed Titanium Alloy Implant Interface Functionalization, *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 10 (2022).
- [4] Z. Hadzhieva, A.R. Boccaccini, Recent developments in electrophoretic deposition (EPD) of antibacterial coatings for biomedical applications - A review, *Curr. Opin. Biomed. Eng.* 21 (2022) 100367.

New materials in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-RE}_2\text{O}_3$ system with interesting optical properties

J. Michalík¹, B. Pecušová², J. Valúchová³, A. Prnová³, R. Klement², D. Galusek^{2,3}

¹ Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology STU, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovakia
(E-mail: jakub.michalik@tnuni.sk)

² Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín,
Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

³ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FchPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Aluminate glasses appear as a possible substitution for polycrystalline aluminates. They show a high chemical and thermal resistance, and a high transmittance for infrared radiation. Doped with rare earth ions they may exhibit up-conversion luminescence, with a potential use in optoelectronic applications as light emitting diodes, amplifiers/modulators, and lasers. One of the frequently used dopants is Er^{3+} , which exhibits luminescence in the green and red regions of the spectrum. The emission properties of Er^{3+} -doped materials can be improved by adding Yb^{3+} as a sensitizer. However, production of aluminate glasses is difficult for their high melting temperatures and a high tendency to crystallization. A possible solution is the preparation of these glasses in a form of microspheres by flame synthesis and by subsequent HP sintering at temperatures up to 1000°C to get bulk glass.

In this work, we focused on the study of Yb^{3+} and Er^{3+} -doped glass microspheres with the perovskite composition (YAIO_3 -YAP). By combination of the Pechini sol-gel method and flame synthesis, we prepared six samples, with different contents of ytterbium and erbium. The prepared microspheres were mostly X-ray amorphous with the presence of YAG, YbAG and traces of YAP in X-ray diffraction patterns. IR and Raman spectroscopy confirmed their amorphous nature with a high degree of disorder in structure. A detailed examination of the surface morphology of prepared particles by SEM did not indicate any presence of crystalline particles. A thorough examination of polished cross sections revealed the presence of needle-like crystals in a small fraction of prepared microspheres, which grew through their whole volume, similarly to YAP crystals observed in reference [1]. An exothermic effect at $926\text{-}927^\circ\text{C}$ was observed in DTA curves in case of all compositions. X-ray powder diffraction analysis of samples after thermal analysis revealed the presence of YAG, YbAG and YAP crystalline phases in treated samples. The observed exothermic effect could be thus assigned to crystallization of these phases. Characteristic green emissions of the Er^{3+} ions at $525\text{-}567\text{ nm}$ and in the red region at $625\text{-}725\text{ nm}$ were observed in the luminescence spectra of prepared glasses. The highest intensity of green emission was obtained in the sample with 25 mol% of Yb_2O_3 . The highest intensity of red emission was obtained in the sample with 30 mol% of Yb_2O_3 , indicating that the amount of added Yb^{3+} significantly affects the optical properties of the studied glasses.

Keywords: erbium, ytterbium, yttrium aluminum garnet, SEM, sol-gel Pechini method, XRD

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566. The financial support of this work by the project APVV 19-0010 is gratefully acknowledged.

Reference:

[1] W. WISNIEWSKI, P. ŠVANČÁREK, A. PRNOVÁ, M. PARCHOVIANSKÝ, D. GALUSEK. $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ microsphere crystallization analyzed by electron backscatter diffraction. In Scientific Reports, 2020, vol. 10, no. 1, art. no. 11122. Available on: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-67816-7>

Synthesis and characterization of YAG: Eu²⁺ and YAG: Eu³⁺ microspheres for LED applications

Marzieh Ghadamyari¹, Róbert Klement¹, Gurdial Blugan³,
Milan Parchoviansky¹, Dušan Galusek^{1,2}, Monika Micháľková²

¹FunGlass – Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, TnUAD, Trenčín, Slovakia

E-mail: marzieh.ghadamyari@tnuni.sk

²Vitrum Laugaricio – Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnU AD, FChPT STU and RONA, a.s., Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovak Republic

³Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology (Empa), Dübendorf 8600, Switzerland

ABSTRACT

Phosphor-converted light-emitting diodes (pc-LEDs) have significant importance due to their applications in solid-state lighting and backlight display. The primary obstacles facing emergent pc-LEDs relate to the attainment of comprehensive spectrum lighting, wide color gamut display, and broadband emission. These factors are contingent upon the luminescence properties of the utilized phosphors. The present study reports the successful synthesis of Eu-doped Y₃Al₅O₁₂ (YAG) phosphors in microsphere form through sol-gel reaction under a reducing N₂:10% H₂ atmosphere. The physical properties of the material were analyzed using various techniques including X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and photoluminescence spectroscopy (PL). A special focus was placed on verifying the presence of Eu²⁺ within the YAG structure. The presence of pure YAG phase in all samples was confirmed by XRD. The Crystal microsphere YAG:Eu²⁺ phosphor exhibited a broad emission spectrum from 450-800 nm, with a maximum peak at 565 nm. This peak is attributed to the allowed 4f₇-4f₆5d₁ electron transition in Eu²⁺ ions.

Keywords: LED, Microspheres, YAG.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

The authors are very grateful to JECS Trust to have the possibility to work at Empa the Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology.

Part of the work in FunGlass was funded by European Union's Horizon 2020, research, and innovation program under grant agreement No 739566. The authors also gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the Slovak Grant Agency of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport, VEGA 1/0456/20.

Processing and microstructure of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG)/ ZrO_2 eutectic ceramics fabricated by spark plasma sintering

M. Vakhshouri¹, A. Najafzadeh², A. Talimian¹, D. Salamon³, K. Maca^{3,4}, D. Galusek^{1,2}

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovak Republic
(maryam.vakhshouri@tnuni.sk)

² Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChFT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovak Republic

³ CEITEC BUT, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123, 612 00 Brno, Czech Republic

⁴ Institute of Materials Science and Engineering, Brno University of Technology, Technická 2, 616 69 Brno, Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

The powder characteristics play an important role in the processing of ceramic materials with the use of powder metallurgy methods. In the present work, the influence of powder treatment techniques, i.e. spheroidization and amorphization, on the sinterability and microstructure of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG)- ZrO_2 composites were investigated. Composite powders with various concentrations of ZrO_2 were synthesized by Pechini's method, spheroidized by flame synthesis, and modified by milling. The amorphization of the powder enabled exploitation of viscous flow during the sintering of the spheroidized powder and, in turn, decreased the sintering temperature with no detrimental impact on the microstructure. The production of irregularly shaped particles from amorphous spheroidized particles by milling further improved sinterability of the composite ceramic powders. The increase of surface area by milling accounts for the improved densification of milled spheroidized powders.

Keywords: $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG)/ ZrO_2 ; Eutectic Ceramics; Spark Plasma Sintering

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

This research work has also been supported by the Research Agency of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic, by the project: Advancement and support of R&D for "Centre for diagnostics and quality testing of materials" in the domains of the RIS3 SK specialization, Acronym: CEDITEK II., ITMS2014+ code 313011W442.

New glass-ceramic and ceramic materials with interesting mechanical properties in the system $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-La}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$

Mohammed Boujida¹, Avnee Chauhan¹, Jakub Michalík², Alena Akusevich¹, Branislav Hruška¹, Helena Pálková³, Jana Valúchová⁴, Anna Prnová⁴, Dušan Galusek⁴

¹ Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

² Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology STU, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovakia

³ Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská cesta 9, 845 36 Bratislava, Slovakia

⁴ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FchPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Technical ceramics, alternatively referred to as advanced ceramics, showcase exceptional performance in specific applications due to their unique composition and structural properties, achieved through precise control over their processing conditions [1]. Alumina (Al_2O_3) [2] and zirconia (ZrO_2) [3] are widely employed as technical ceramics in various industrial applications.

This study will focus on the investigation of precursor powders in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-La}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$ system and their subsequent processing into microspheres using flame synthesis. The synthesized microspheres will be characterized using various techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), differential thermal analysis/thermogravimetry (DTA/TG), optical microscopy (OM), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The prepared microspheres will be subjected to hot-press sintering and spark plasma sintering techniques to obtain bulk of glasses or glass ceramics materials.

Under the framework of this project, primarily two different compositions of ALaZ10 (45 mol % Al_2O_3 , 45 mol % La_2O_3 , 10 mol % ZrO_2) and ALaZ20 (40 mol % Al_2O_3 , 40 mol % La_2O_3 , 20 mol % ZrO_2) were prepared by sol-gel Pechini method. The received powders were calcinated at 650°C for 6h and 1000°C for 12h, and then sintered at 1200°C for 12h. X-ray, IR and Raman spectroscopy were used for detailed examination of structure changes of materials after individual stages of heat treatment. The broad shoulder in interval 20-40° in 2 theta range (X-ray patterns), wide bands in interval 400-800 cm^{-1} (IR spectra), and in interval 200-1000 cm^{-1} (Raman spectra) confirm the amorphous nature with high degree of disorder in raw materials after sol-gel preparation. On the contrary, in X ray patterns of samples annealed at different temperatures (650°C, 1000°C and 1200°C), typical diffractions of LaAlO_3 , ZrO_2 , LaZrO_2 crystalline phases were observed. The intensity of individual diffractions increased with increasing of temperature. The crystalline nature of the samples was also confirmed by IR and Raman spectroscopy. The typical IR vibrations in the range 400-800 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to motions of M—O bonds (M=Al, La) and Raman vibrations in interval 200-1000 cm^{-1} confirms the creation and existence of LaAlO_3 , ZrO_2 and LaZrO_2 crystalline phases in the samples. The prepared powders will be used as a starting material for flame synthesis of glass microspheres.

Keywords: alumina, ceramic, lanthanum, sol-gel Pechini method, XRD, zirconia.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

References:

- [1] W.R. Matizamhuka Advanced ceramics — The new frontier in modern-day technology: Part I J. South. African Inst. Min. Metall., 118 (2018), pp. 757-764.
- [2] A.M. Abyzov Aluminum Oxide and Alumina Ceramics (review). Part 1. Properties of Al_2O_3 and Commercial Production of Dispersed Al_2O_3 Refract. Ind. Ceram., 60 (2019), pp. 24-32.
- [3] K. Matsui, H. Yoshida, Y. Ikuhara Review: microstructure-development mechanism during sintering in polycrystalline zirconia Int. Mater. Rev., 63 (2018), pp. 375-406.

Polymer derived ceramic coatings reinforced with $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ powder

Parisa. N. Moghaddam¹, Milan. Parchovianský¹, Ivana. Parchovianská¹,
Amirhossein. Pakseresh¹

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín
(E-mail: parisa.moghaddam@tnuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

Polymer derived ceramics (PDCs) is an appropriate material for preparing protective coatings due to their excellent oxidation and corrosion resistance at elevated temperatures [1]. However, the primary challenge of this approach is the remarkable shrinkage during polymer-to-ceramic conversion. One way to compensate for high volume shrinkage is to add suitable filler particles in the coating slurry. In addition, fillers can be utilized to adjust and improve the thermal and structural stability of PDC coatings. In this work, $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ (LZ) powder has been selected as a promising filler material for PDC coatings because of its excellent thermal stability, high melting point (2300 °C), and low thermal conductivity [2]. For this purpose, LZ ceramic powder was synthesized by high temperature solid state reaction (SSR). The synthesized LZ powder was heat-treated at 1400 °C for 6 h and some properties, such as powder morphology, chemical composition, and thermal stability, were investigated after high temperature treatment. A single pyrochlore phase of LZ was detected by XRD after annealing at 1400 °C. The thermal behavior of LZ powder was investigated by DSC and TGA in the temperature range of 25–1300 °C. A significant mass change was not observed in the tested temperature range, proving the high thermal stability of LZ powder. Barium aluminosilicate (BAS) glass was synthesized to be incorporated into coating compositions. Then, the coating system, consisting of a Durazane 2250 bond coat and a top coat (Durazane 1800 + LZ filler + BAS glass), was prepared. A double-layer PDC coating was applied to stainless steel substrates by the dip-coating technique. In this work, different top coat slurries were prepared to optimize the coating. After pyrolysis in the air at 850 °C, the XRD results showed the presence of a single LZ phase. Based on results obtained from SEM, the optimum suspension was crack-free and dense; only a few small pores were observed.

Keywords: Fillers, Organosilicon Precursor, PDC coatings, Pyrolysis, Solid state reaction, Thermal stability

Acknowledgment:

This work was created in the frame of the project Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalised Glass (CEGLASS), ITMS code 313011R453, operational program Research and Innovation, co-funded from European Regional Development Fund. This work is a part of dissemination activities of project FunGlass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566. The authors also gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the project VEGA no. 1/0171/21.

References:

- [1] Q. Wen, Z. Yu, R. Riedel, Progress in Materials Science, 109, 100623 (2020).
- [2] J. Zhang, X. Guo, Y. G. Jung, L. Li, & J. Knapp, Surface and Coatings Technology, 323, 18-29 (2017).

Methodology for evaluation of corrosion resistance in AZS refractory materials during the production of Ba crystalline glass

Sheeraz Khan^{1*}, Jozef Kraxner¹, Peter Vrábel²

¹*Department of Glass Processing, FunGlass, Centre for functional and surface functionalized glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia*

²*RONA, a.s., Schreiberova 365, 020 61 Lednické Rovne, Slovakia*

(E-mail: sheeraz.khan@tnuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

The corrosion resistance in AZS refractory materials during the production of Ba crystalline glass is a crucial aspect to ensure the performance of the AZS refractory materials. Many ways have been investigated to improve refractory materials' corrosion resistance, including using additives and coatings, modification of material composition, and processing condition optimization. In this study, the corrosion resistance of the AZS refractory materials will be evaluated using various techniques and lab-scale tests such as (static and dynamic tests, hot stage microscopy, crucible test, finger test, rotating finger test, and etc.) with a new radar and ultrasound NDT technique, microstructural analysis, and chemical analysis of the corroded surfaces. The results obtained from these evaluations will provide valuable insights into the performance and durability of the refractory materials, aiding in the selection of AZS material and optimization of the melting condition for Ba crystalline glass production. This research will provide an overview of the mechanisms of corrosion, issues of refractory corrosion in the industrial sector, refractory degradation, properties and durability in refractory materials, and the strategies that have been employed to enhance their resistance to corrosion. The work also highlights some of the challenges that remain in the field, including the need to develop more accurate corrosion behavior models and optimize the design and selection of refractory materials for specific applications. This study aims to enable manufacturers to improve the corrosion resistance of AZS refractory materials, resulting in enhanced efficiency and cost-effectiveness during the production of Ba crystalline glass.

Keywords: AZS refractory materials, corrosion process, Ba crystalline glass.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

Sono-photo hybrid catalytic process for the degradation of Tetracycline

S. Sajjadi and R. Klement

Dept. of Functional Materials, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50
Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: mir.sajjadi@tuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

Recently, combination of various advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) have been applied to treat detrimental compounds from wastewater. Sonophotocatalysis within AOPs can manifest the high degradation of a broad domain of contaminants [1]. Bismuth tungstate (Bi_2WO_6) is an n-type, narrow band gap (2.8–3.0 eV) semiconductor and has been considered as promising catalyst. Despite its high photocatalytic activity, pristine Bi_2WO_6 is not ideal due to rapid charge recombination after light absorption [2]. Indium sulfide (In_2S_3) semiconductors have a narrow bandgap of approximately 2.4 eV [3] compared with typical photocatalysts such as TiO_2 (3.2 eV) [3] and ZnO (3.37 eV) [4]. In_2S_3 also shows an outstanding visible light response with a high absorption coefficient of $1.65 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [5], which is notably higher than that of TiO_2 and ZnO . These properties make In_2S_3 a promising candidate for photocatalytic applications. However, the slow charge carrier separation and migration kinetics of a pristine In_2S_3 photocatalyst limits its catalytic performance. Additionally, magnetic supports could overcome the limitation of separation from the liquid phase, thus the catalyst could be effectively recycled by applying an external magnetic field [6]. Hence, in this study, the Z-scheme $\text{In}_2\text{S}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{WO}_6/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ magnetic core-shell structure catalyst was prepared and sonophotocatalytic degradation of tetracycline (TC) was studied.

The prepared catalyst was characterized by SEM, EDX, DRS, and XPS. In addition, the catalytic activity of the $\text{In}_2\text{S}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{WO}_6/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ catalyst was investigated by sonophotocatalytic degradation of TC. The 0.5 g/L of $\text{In}_2\text{S}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{WO}_6/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ dispersed in solution with pH=6.5 and TC (10 mg/L) showed a high degradation efficiency of TC (94.7% within 60 min), under visible LED light (50 W) and ultrasound (140 W) irradiation. This high catalytic activity of the $\text{In}_2\text{S}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{WO}_6/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ core-shell catalyst was mainly attributed to the synergistic effects of the formed interfaces between the shell and core, which generate an electric field to facilitate charge transfer. Additionally, direct Z-scheme heterojunction inhibits e^- and h^+ charge recombination and expands light absorption in the visible range. Furthermore, the results expressed the presence of synergy between the combined systems (sonocatalysis and photocatalysis). $\text{In}_2\text{S}_3/\text{Bi}_2\text{WO}_6/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ showed good reusability and stability.

Keywords: Core-shell catalyst; Advanced oxidation processes; Bismuth tungstate; Indium sulfide; Tetracycline.

References

- [1] Matafonova, G.; Batoev, V. *Water Research* **2019**, 166, 115085.
- [2] Shiamala, L.; Vignesh, K.; Jaffar Ali, B.M. *Fuel* **2023**, 333, 126332.
- [3] D. Ma, W. Liu, Q. Chen, Z. Jin, Y. Zhang, J. Huang, H. Zhang, F. Peng, T. Luo, *J Solid State Chem* **2021**, 293, 121791.
- [4] N.R. Khalid, A. Hammad, M.B. Tahir, M. Rafique, T. Iqbal, G. Nabi, M.K. Hussain, *Ceram Int* **2019**, 45, 21430.
- [5] A. Kennedy, H. Ganesan, R. Marnadu, S.K. Kannan, S.I. Arockiam, M. Ubaidullah, M. Shkir, S. AlFaify, S. Gedi, *Opt Mater (Amst)* **2022**, 124, 111769.
- [6] Zhang, L.; Wang, W.; Zhou, L.; Shang, M.; Sun, S. *Applied Catalysis B* **2009**, 90, 458–462.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.